

Final Report

Artisanal Fishing Patterns Mapping Survey – Southern Coast of Tanzania

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UEI Number: K6J6P2MTC2W8
4. Submitted to: USAID Heshimu Bahari Activity
5. Grant Title: Artisanal Fishing Patterns Mapping Survey – Southern Coast of Tanzania Mainland.
6. Grant Agreement No.: FAA-AFO-006
7. Grant Period: Start Date: December 20, 2023 - Completion Date: March 14, 2024.

19th February 2024

Disclaimer

This report is made possible by the support of the American People through the United States Agency for International Development (USAID). The content of this report is the sole responsibility of Aqua-Farms Organization for USAID/Tanzania under Chemonics and does not necessarily reflect the views of USAID or the United States Government.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was funded by Chemonics under the USAID Heshimu Bahari Activity and implemented by Aqua-Farms Organization. We gratefully acknowledge the Fisheries Officers from Kigamboni, Kinondoni, Mkuranga, Kibiti, Mafia, Kilwa, Lindi, and Mtama districts for their support during the implementation of this project, particularly during the fieldwork. We would like to extend special thanks to the local coastal communities, BMUs, VLCs, and village authorities for their willingness to accept, support, and fully participate in the Focus Group Discussions in 108 BMUs/villages across the project areas. This work could not be possible without the dedicated team of data collectors; we also extend our gratitude for their excellent work during the fieldwork. Finally, the team would like to thank the Local Government Authorities in the respective project sites for their support and guidance in successfully enhancing the achievement of the project and their commitment to the conservation and management of marine and coastal resources in Tanzania.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AFO	Aqua - Farms Organization
AFPM	Artisanal Fishing Patterns Mapping
BMU	Beach Management Unit
CFMA	Collaborative Fisheries Management Area
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
FPM	Fishing Patterns Mapping
FRZs	Fisheries Replenishment Zones
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
LGAs	Local Government Authorities
MMA	Marine Management Areas
MPAs	Marine Protected Areas
TAFIRI	Tanzania Fisheries Research Institute
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
VLCs	Village Liaison Committees
WCS	Wildlife Conservation Society

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report highlights the achievements of the USAID Heshimu Bahari activity to undertake Artisanal Fishing Patterns Mapping (AFPM) survey along the Southern Coast of Tanzania Mainland. The activity has been implemented by Aqua-Farms Organization, with an ultimate aim to gather crucial insights from coastal communities within Collaborative Fisheries Management Areas (CFMAs) and other management areas, between Dar es Salaam and Lindi, contributing to the development of a science-driven framework for sustainable Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and co-management of wild-caught fisheries in Tanzania Mainland and Zanzibar. The primary objective of the Fishing Patterns Mapping (FPM) was to generate geographically referenced data that intricately detailed the behavior of fishing activities based on different gear types within the designated project area. This information served as a foundation for a multi-parametric marine spatial analysis, guiding the identification of optimal locations for establishing No-Take Fisheries Replenishment Zones (FRZs).

The comprehensive scope of work encompassed mapping fishing grounds, creating metadata for each ground, evaluating relative usage by each Beach Management Unit (BMU), and assigning ratings for overall use, fish productivity, and livelihood importance. This expansive survey spanned 23 Management Areas, including Marine Reserves, CFMAs, and MPAs, engaging 108 BMUs, villages, and Village Liaison Committees. The methodological approach was structured, beginning with the preparation of materials, followed by a desk-based analysis of gear use, and field data collection through Focus Group Discussions. Experienced fishers, with a minimum of 5 years in specific gear usage, actively participated. Mapped fishing grounds underwent digitization on Google Earth and provided a platform for validation and harmonization with community members.

Engagement meetings with key stakeholders, such as Heshimu Bahari and the Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS), were pivotal in aligning methodologies and exchanging project insights. The key phases, including preparation, hand mapping, digitization, and harmonization, were discussed during these sessions. Essential action points emerged, including data validation, training sessions, and on-field engagement.

The organizational structure of the team was well-organized with a strong team comprising the team leads, technical advisors, and GIS experts. This main team was complemented by 33 dedicated data collectors, each with a specific role in data collection and community engagement. Team leads were designated for each CFMA or Management Area, ensuring a focused and tailored approach.

This report entails a summary of all the activities done, methodologies, implementation status, results and achievements, challenges, recommendations, lessons learned throughout the project period.

I INTRODUCTION

I.1 Background

The coastline of Tanzania, spanning over 1400 km is endowed with rich ecosystems including coral reefs, seagrass meadows, mangroves which are the home of diverse organisms. , These ecosystems and associated organisms provide immense contribution to improving livelihood through the opportunities it provides for income and employment. However, due to poor management, unsustainable harvesting practices and climate change have led to drastic decline in coastal and marine resources. This decline endangers livelihoods of coastal fisheries dependent communities and jeopardizes food security. The challenges are also exacerbated by the lack of a functional marine management area (MMA) framework, inadequate governance systems, insufficient financing, and a lack of incentives to the private sector. In response, Heshimu Bahari aims to establish an enabling environment and a science-driven framework for sustainable MMA and wild-caught fishery co-management involving the government, communities, and the private sector. Aqua-Farms Organization (AFO) has thus commissioned a grant to conduct the Artisanal Fishing Patterns Mapping (AFPM) survey along the Southern Coast of Tanzania Mainland, contributing to addressing these critical challenges.

This ultimate goal of the activity is to gather data from coastal communities within Collaborative Fisheries Management Areas (CFMAs) which will inform the establishment of a scientifically informed framework for sustainable marine protected areas (MPAs) and co-management of wild-caught fisheries in both Tanzania Mainland and Zanzibar.

The survey specifically targeted the southern coast of Tanzania Mainland in 8 districts namely Kigamboni, Kinondoni, Mkuranga, Kibiti, Mafia, Kilwa, Lindi and Mtama. This included 23 Management Areas, incorporating Marine Reserves, CFMAs, and MPAs, spanning across 108 Beach Management Units (BMUs), villages, and Village Liaison Committees (VLCs). Key stakeholders involved in this endeavor included fishers, CFMA leaders, Beach Management Units, village leaders, and Fisheries Officers.

The survey methodology entailed conducting Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with fishers within each CFMA, who were identified based on specific fishing gear usage. Approximately 5 to 6 commonly utilized fishing gears as well as additional seaweed farming spots were identified within each CFMA. Each gear type was represented by two fishers with a minimum of 5 years of fishing experience and residency within the respective village of the CFMA for at least 5 years. The FGD sessions covered various activities, including completing metadata forms, identifying fishing grounds, and delineating these grounds on printed maps. Furthermore, the mapped fishing grounds were digitized using Google Earth and subsequently validated by the participating fishers.

I.2 Goal of the Activity

The goal of the Fishing Patterns Mapping (FPM) within the Heshimu Bahari initiative is to produce geographically referenced data detailing the behaviour of fishing activities based on different gear types throughout the designated project area. This information will be utilized in a multi-parametric marine spatial analysis, using the Marxan approach, to pinpoint ideal locations for establishing No-Take Fisheries Replenishment Zones (FRZs).

2 METHODOLOGIES

2.1 Project site

The activity was conducted in 108 villages (BMUs/VNRCs) in 8 coastal districts in mainland Tanzania from namely Kigamboni, Kinondoni, Mkuranga, Kibiti, Mafia, Kilwa, Lindi rural and Mtama. The Artisanal Fishing Patterns Mapping survey was conducted between December and February 2024. The Appendix II shows the list of all villages in the project locations.

2.2 Data Collection and Analysis

The collection of data from the villages included a Desk Review of existing gray literature and check sheets and questionnaires for Focus Group Discussion. Data were then digitized and visualized on the [Google Earth Pro version 7.3.6](#) as explained below:

I. Introductory Meetings

An introductory meeting for the activity was conducted in each of the study sites to introduce the activity and ask the concerned authority (Local Government Authority) on the possibilities of conducting the activity in their area. The objectives of these meetings were to highlight and familiarize the LGAs and particularly the Fisheries Department about the activity and the expectations.

II. Preparation of materials

- The A3 maps were prepared and printed for each targeted Community-Based Fisheries Management Area (CFMA). Shapefiles were provided, ensuring accuracy and detailed representation. These maps were designed to include essential details that assisted fishers in easily identifying their respective fishing grounds.
- Desk-based analysis of gear-use to identify primary gears in each CFMA:

Fishing gears in each village were systematically mapped through a comprehensive process involving desktop analysis, interviews with Fisheries Officers and Beach Management Units (BMUs), and, in certain areas, engagement with village leaders. Approximately 5 to 6 of the most commonly used fishing gears were selected for the AFPM survey in each village.

III. Field data collection process in each CFMA

- Identification of key informant fishers

The selection of key informant fishers per Community-Based Fisheries Management Area (CFMA) was undertaken in collaboration with BMU and village leaders, under the coordination of fisheries officers in respective districts. Fishers were selected based on their gears whereby two fishers from each fishing gear were selected. Experience was also considered whereby for a fisherman to be considered in the survey should have at least 5 years of experience in the respective area/village and fishing activities.

- Focus Group Discussion

FGD enabled collection of comprehensive data from the fishers. The data collection process involved small groups of fishers using the same fishing gear grouped together. Fishers were first oriented with the exercise and specifically the maps until and it was clear, and they were able to identify various locations. A trained data collector facilitated the discussions and filled in a metadata form by posing relevant questions to the participants, particularly fishers. In addition to verbal responses, fishers were immediately asked to identify their specific fishing grounds which they normally fish in each season, drawing polygons to represent each ground on the A3 printed maps. To ensure accuracy, the data collector guided the fishers by indicating reference points and/or any other features on the printed maps, facilitating precise location identification and accurate drawing of the fishing grounds.

IV. Data digitization and visualization

- Digitization

After the fishers complete drawing on the printed maps, the data collector continued to digitize the drawn fishing grounds on [Google Earth Pro version 7.3.6](#) using a laptop. Once digitized, the maps were visualized and presented to the gear-specific focus group for validation using a projector. This step ensured accuracy and alignment with the fishers' inputs.

3. IMPLEMENTATION STATUS

The implementation status of the project has progressed smoothly, with all outlined tasks and milestones completed and submitted as per schedule. The inception report provided a comprehensive overview of the project's objectives and methodologies, setting a solid foundation for subsequent activities. Recruitment reports for staff, consultants, and field data collectors were successfully executed, ensuring the project team was adequately equipped with the necessary expertise and manpower. Meeting reports, including updates to the methodology and implementation plan, have been documented and circulated among stakeholders, facilitating transparent communication and alignment of project activities.

The artisanal fishing gear profile was well compiled, offering valuable insights into the gear types utilized in respective BMUs and VLCs. Meeting reports with attendance lists of fishers, village leaders and BMU leaders have been documented, fostering community engagement and collaboration throughout the project duration. Primary maps, scanned copies of A3-size maps, and digital shapefiles of fishing ground boundaries have been generated, providing a spatial representation of fishing grounds in between Dar es Salaam and Lindi.

Furthermore, an Excel sheet containing comprehensive data has been maintained, ensuring accuracy and accessibility of project information. Georeferenced maps, points, and boundaries for each fishing ground have been developed, all sent to Chemonics USAID Heshimu Bahari and

WCS. Finally, final A0 size maps generated by each pair of gear representatives from each BMU in each CFMA were not produced as during the methodology review with WCS and USAID Heshimu Bahari they were no longer necessary to produce. Overall, the project has achieved all milestones within the designated timeline. A success story has been annexed (Appendix I) in this report.

4. RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

During the preparatory and implementation phases, fishing gear profiling was conducted across the project activity sites ([Activity Report](#)). The survey revealed varying degrees of diversity in the types of fishing gear used, with a total of 14 different fishing gears identified. NYAMANJISOPOJA CFMA exhibited the highest diversity, with 12 different fishing gears identified, followed by Site PEPUKIBUKWA (10), TIM4SI (9), JOJIBAKI (9), and MKURANGA (8), while KIMSA and MKISAMI CFMAs had relatively fewer types of fishing gears, 4 gears (Figure 1). From this study, 5 to 6 common fishing gears were selected to conduct the Artisanal Fishing Patterns Mapping (AFPM) survey in each BMU or village.

Fig 1: A graph showing the type and number of fishing gears profiled by each management area.

The project has engaged more than 600 participants across the targeted coastline covering 23 Management Areas, over 108 BMU and VLCs. The participation was representative of both male and female stakeholders where 14.3% were females and 85.7% were males (Figure 2). The participation of females was relatively small due to the nature of fishing activities in Tanzania, as it is still a male dominated industry and women are restricted to near shore activities and fishing gears such as Spear, Gleaning, Fencing, Seaweed farming and local processing while men crosscut across all fishing gears.

Gender representation from participants

Fig 2: Pie chart showing gender representation of survey participants excluding AFO staff.

Below is a milestone table showing the status of each milestone as per Agreement.

Table I: Shows Milestone and Status of the Activities

Milestone Description	Verification of Milestone	Status
<p>Milestone I:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Engagement with Heshimu Bahari ● Signing of contracts (consultants and field data collectors) ● Consultative meeting with WCS and USAID Heshimu Bahari Team ● Team alignment workshop to familiarize with the ● Methodology and desk review of former fish pattern survey. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inception report ● Recruitment report for staff, consultants, and field data collectors ● Meeting report including the updated methodology and updated implementation plan 	<p>All tasks under milestone completed and submitted to Heshimu Bahari and WCS</p>

<p>Milestone 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Preliminary desk-based analysis to develop a profile of artisanal fishing gear used in each of the 107 BMU villages and 25. ● CFMAs & Mgt areas. ● Hold introductory meetings with village and BMU. ● leaders in each village to introduce the activity, discuss focus group selection. ● Convene 2 key-informant fishers for commonly used fishing gear from each BMU within the CFMA, forming focus groups to validate gear selection. ● Sketching Draft Maps and consolidated mapping ● Digitization and validation of maps and rating of fishing grounds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Artisanal fishing gear profile ● Meeting reports with a list of attendees who are village leaders and BMU leaders. ● Primary maps ● Scanned copies of A3-size maps generated by each pair of gear representatives from each BMU. ● Digital shapefiles of fishing ground boundaries for each gear-wise map 	<p>All tasks under milestone completed and submitted to Heshimu Bahari and WCS</p>
<p>Milestone 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Qualitative data collection ● Plenary Session for ● Consolidation ● Geo-Referencing, Position Fixing Exercise and Reference Point Fixation ● Validation with fishers and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Excel sheet with data ● Meeting Report ● Georeferenced maps, Points and Boundaries for each fishing ground ● Final A0 size maps generated by each pair of gear representatives 	<p>All tasks under milestone completed and submitted to Heshimu Bahari and WCS with exception to Final A0 sized Maps - Which was no longer required by WCS according to meeting done</p>

key informants	from each BMU in each CFMA	during inception
<p>Milestone 4:</p> <p>End of project Report</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Maximum of 30 pages Comprehensive final activity report incorporating all the activities output, challenges, solutions, and recommendations ● Submit separately at least 30 high quality photos covering the important events during the activity implementation. ● Submit as an annex a success story. 	<p>All tasks under milestone completed and submitted to Heshimu Bahari and WCS</p>

5. IMPLEMENTATION CHALLENGES

- Heavy rains and rough roads hindered fishers' mobility and access to meeting areas, impacting transportation and scheduling.
- Difficulties with network, electricity, and generator availability necessitated the use of multiple providers and backup systems, affecting data collection and event operations.
- Mafia District Authority's requirement for an introduction letter caused a delay in data collection timing, highlighting bureaucratic hurdles in project implementation.
- Challenges in communication and perception arose, including fishers' reluctance to share information and concerns about boundary delineation, necessitating clear explanations and awareness campaigns.

- Unforeseen division of BMU into two new BMU within the Kilwa Masoko BMU led to additional costs and attendees, while changes in activity schedules and disruptions in power supply increased expenses and logistical complexities, underscoring the importance of adaptive resource management strategies.

6. LESSONS LEARNED AND ADAPTATION

- Engaging fishers in artisanal fishing patterns mapping surveys is crucial for gathering accurate data, fostering community involvement and ownership, and promoting sustainable fisheries management.
- Early acquisition of clearance and permit is important for timely and effective execution of project activities. It minimizes bureaucratic obstacles and potential setbacks.
- Conducting inception meetings and awareness raising for both policy and decision makers and local communities before launching the project in the respective areas is crucial. This process ensures that stakeholders at various levels are well-informed, sharing a common understanding of the project's objectives and anticipated outcomes. This, in turn, minimizes misconceptions and hesitancy during the implementation phase, contributing to the overall success of the project.
- Conducting baseline surveys and leveraging data from previous projects are crucial steps in project planning. However, it has come to our attention that certain areas have already experienced similar activities conducted by other organizations. This has led to duplication of efforts and confusion among local communities due to the repetition of similar activities in the same area.
- It's important to harmonize data during the fieldwork on a daily basis between the meta data, maps and the relative usage data to reduce chances of error, repetition and much use of time in data cleaning.
- During designing of primary maps, it is necessary to not use Google earth printed maps as they have heavily blue colored background which affects visibility but rather use deduced maps from the shapefile sourced through QGIS or ArcGIS.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Engaging Feedback meeting: Participants in the AFPM survey expressed the need to conduct feedback meetings with the BMUs to ensure effective communication and mutual understanding of the project progress and findings.
- It would be beneficial to provide the final maps of these fishing grounds to the Beach Management Units (BMUs), as they will be useful during their co-management meetings in their respective Community-Based Fisheries Management Areas (CFMAs).

8. CONCLUSION

The Artisanal Fishing Pattern Mapping survey has been successfully completed. Geographically referenced data detailing the behavior of fishing activities based on different gear types throughout the designated project area has been generated. This activity has laid the groundwork for identifying priority marine areas for enhanced protection and management, including the establishment of No-Take Fisheries Replenishment Zones (FRZs). The success of the activity is attributed to the close engagement of local communities, village authorities, and local government authorities, who are the primary resource users. The involvement of these stakeholders, particularly the local coastal communities, has provided invaluable insights leveraging local knowledge that will be incorporated into decision-making processes. Furthermore, it has increased conservation commitment in Tanzania among the target stakeholders, including local communities, village authorities, and local government authorities.

9. APPENDICES

Appendix I: Success Story

Title: Artisanal Fisheries Mapping for Better Marine Management in the Southern Coast of Tanzania Mainland

In early 2024, Aqua-Farms Organization, in collaboration with USAID Heshimu Bahari, embarked on a transformative journey along the Southern Coast of Tanzania Mainland under the execution of the “Artisanal Fisheries Patterns Mapping” (AFPM) survey. The mapping aimed at gathering crucial insights from coastal communities within Marine Managed Areas such as Collaborative Fisheries Management Areas (CFMAs) and Marine Reserves and Marine Parks in order to contribute to the development of a science-driven framework for sustainable Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and co-management of wild-caught fisheries in Tanzania Mainland and Zanzibar. The primary objective of this activity was to generate geographically referenced data that details the behavior of fishing activities based on different gear types within the southern coast of Tanzania stretching from Dar es Salaam to Lindi. The mapping covered 23 Management Areas including Marine Reserves, CFMAs, and MPAs, engaged about 108 Beach Management Units (BMUs), villages, and Village Liaison Committees. In order to accomplish this work timely, team effort was necessary, therefore:

A dynamic team of approximately 33 youth data collectors with backgrounds in Fisheries and Geographic Information System (GIS) were firstly recruited and underwent a series of training on data collection and digitization process in collaboration with Wildlife Conservation Society (WCS) and Heshimu Bahari. The training entailed: mapping fishing grounds, creating metadata for each area, evaluating relative usage by each BMU, and assigning ratings for overall use, fish productivity, and livelihood importance, community interaction and piloting. At the end of the training, the data collectors not only contributed to the project execution and success but also testified on having experienced personal and professional growth. Each team had designated leads for a respective Marine Managed Area which aided in fostering leadership skills and teamwork spirit amongst them.

Photo 1 & 2: Pictures showing ongoing training of the AFPM survey to the data collectors prior going to field, conducted at Aqua-Farms Offices

The teams used 8-14 days of fieldwork in their respective CFMAs to accomplish the assigned tasks and required deliverables on site, throughout all teams it was noted that: **“Collaboration with local fishing communities is vital in achieving success of data collection”**.

“Trust has to be earned by showing respect and engaging in respectful conversations”
 Paschal Temba, a team lead from PEPUKIBUGWA CFMA. Various insights were gained during data collection and interactions which includes local knowledge exchange and data on the fishing grounds, the fishing gears, and the fish species; Fortunately, from this work, there was a great success on willingness of the local fishing communities to actively engage and participate in the fishing grounds mapping process which made the work fun and enjoyable for the teams involved, this was through the cooperation received from the fisheries officers and the local government authorities

Apart from data collection, other outcomes noted by the team included:

- Enhanced understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by the particular local fishing communities.
- Established collaborative relationships between Aqua-Farms organization, USAID Heshimu Bahari and other stakeholders in the management areas.
- Captured knowledge of the fishing gears and fishing grounds through questionnaires and mapping exercises.

Photo 3: Picture showing community engagement at Mafia Island Marine Park during the data harmonization phase.

Despite the successes, the initiative faced several challenges, including power cuts, high transportation costs exceeding the budget, and unexpected additional expenses. However, in the face of adversity, the teams showcased remarkable resilience, creativity and maintained effective communication. Miss Florian Florian, Team Lead at SOMAKI CFMA, aptly summarized the approach to these challenges: ***"Being flexible is key; nothing is set in stone. Knowing when and how to adapt really helped."***

Some of the major lessons learned include recognizing the importance of embracing indigenous knowledge for achieving sustainable management areas. Additionally, employing familiar terms related to fishing gears and practices ensures the message is easily comprehensible and relatable which minimizes the risk of misunderstandings due to miscommunication. Lastly, the initiative highlighted the significance of respect and empathy in conducting community discussions, acknowledging the importance of understanding and valuing the perspectives of local communities.

"Indigenous knowledge can play a pivotal role in identifying ecologically sensitive areas and guiding sustainable management practices. This not only promotes the conservation of marine resources but also supports the livelihoods of fishing communities." - Joyce Mganga, NYAMANJISOPOJA CFMA Team Lead

The insights gathered from this survey will form the bedrock for identifying locations to establish No-Take Fisheries Replenishment Zones (FRZs). This success story goes beyond mapping patterns; it's about crafting a sustainable future for marine resources and the communities that rely on them, this is in total alignment with Aqua-Farms Organization vision of apprehending coastal communities' livelihoods while championing marine conservation, we look forward to working further with USAID Heshimu Bahari, local fishing communities and other stakeholders in realizing this vision for our country.

Appendix 2: A table showing a list of BMU and VLC and their clustering.

District	Management Area	BMU	Meeting Point	Number of BMU in a meeting
Kinondoni	Mbudya & Pangavini MRs	Kunduchi	Kunduchi	3
	Bongoyo Island	Msasani		
	Marine Reserve	Kawe		
	Fungu Yasini MR	Ununio	Ununio	2
Mbweni				
Kigamboni	MJIMWOGEMAFE CFMA including 3x marine reserves: Kendwa, Makatube Islands & Sinda Islands	Ferry	Ferry	2
		Magogoni		
		Gezaulole	Mjimwema	3
		Mwongozo		
		Mjimwema		
	MKISAMI CFMA	Mbutu Mkwajuni	Minondo	3
		Sara- Kichangani		
		Minondo		
KINGOMIKWA CFMA	Kizito Huonjwa	Ngobanya	2	
	Ngobanya			

		Mikenge		
		Kwa Chale	Mikenge	2
	PEPUKIBUKWA CFMA	Kwa Morisi		
		Puna		
		Kibungo	Puna	3
		Buyuni Centre - Mahenge		
		Pemba Centre - Gurubwida	Buyuni Centre	2
Mkuranga	None yet CFMAs establishment process is underway	Kwale		
		Koma		
		Kisiju	Kisiju	3
		Kibewa		
		Mpafu	Mpafu	2
	None yet CFMAs establishment process is underway	Nganje		
		Mdimni	Nganje	2
		Mchabike A		
		Mchabike B	Mchabike A	2
		None yet CFMAs establishment process is underway	Kuruti	
Boza			2	

Kibiti	MSIKIVI CFMA	Kivinja A	Kivinja A	2
		Msindaji		
	KIMSA CFMA	Kiomboni	Nyamisati	2
		Msala		
	MCHIMCHUNYA CFMA	Mchinga	Nyamisati	2
		Mfisini		
		Mchungu	Nyamisati	2
		Nyamisati		
	MBWEKIEKI CFMA	Mbwera Mashariki	Muhoro	2
		Mbwera Magharibi		
		Kiasi	Muhoro	2
		Kiechuru		
	none	Kiongoroni	Muhoro	2
		Ruma		
Mafia	JOJIBAKI CFMA	Jojo	Kirongwe	2
		Jimbo		
		Banja	Banja	2
		Kirongwe		
	DOKICHUNDA CFMA	Dongo	Kilindoni	2

		Ndagoni		
		Chunguruma		
		Kilindoni	Kilindoni	2
	Mafia Island Marine Park	Chole		
		Juani	Kidiwani	2
		Jibondo		
		Kungwi	Kidiwani	2
		Baleni		
		Marimbani		
		Kiegeani / Utende	Kidiwani	3
		Chem Chem		
		Miburani	Kidiwani	2
		Mlongo		
		Kilindoni (Bwejuu)	Kidiwani	2
		Ndagoni		
	Jimbo	Kidiwani	2	
Kilwa	NYAMANJISOPOJA CFMA	Songosongo		
		Njianne	Songo Songo	2
		Somanga south	Somanga	2

		Somanga north		
		Nyamatungutungu	Nyamatungutungu	2
		Marendego		
		Pombwe (Kibiti)		
		Jaja (Kibiti)	Jaja	2
		Mtukwao		
		Magengeni,	Kilwa Kivinje	2
		Mgongeni		
		Singino	Kilwa Kivinje	2
		Mtandango		
		Tingi	Kilwa Kivinje	2
		Mtoni		
	TIM4SI CFMA	Miteja	Kilwa Kivinje	2
		Songomnara		
		masoko Mjini	Kilwa Masoko	2
	SOMAKI CFMA	Mnazi mmoja	Kilwa Masoko	1
		Kisiwani	Kilwa Masoko	1
	Have proposed to join SOMAKI CFMA but not yet formalized	Malalani		
		Mtitimiria	Pande	3

		Namwedo		
	KIRULINA CFMA - under process of establishment	NakimweraMikoma	Lihimalyao Kaskazini	2
		Namakongoro		
		Lihimalyao Kaskazini	Lihimalyao Kaskazini	2
		Lihimalyao Kusini		
		Kisongo	Rushungi	3
		Kiswere		
		Rushungi		
Lindi Mjini	KIJIMVUMALO	Kijiweni	Nachunyu	3
		Mvuleni Mashariki		
		Maloo		
	MCHIRUVU	Mchinga 1	Nachunyu	3
		Mchinga 2		
		Ruvu		
Mtama	SHUMMOSU	Shuka	Navanga	2
		Mangomango		
	SHUMMOSU	Mmumbu	Navanga	2
		Sudi		

Appendix 3: Example of metadata

Date	BMU Villages	Gear code	Gear Name	Gear Name Official	Fishing Ground	Ku_F1	Ku_F2	Ku_F3	Ka_F1	Ka_F2	Ka_F3	Mammals	Sea turtles	Sharks	Rays	Overall	Productivity	Livelihood	Spwan_Yw	Spwan_No	Species_1	Species_2	Species_3	Permanent	Temporary	Note	KMZ_file_name	folder_name	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G5		Mahipi wakulumbu Longlines	Kwa Koba		0	10	0	0	0	4	1	1	1	1	5	5	4	1	0	Taii	Changu		0	1		0 G5_Long line_Koba	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G5		Mahipi wakulumbu Longlines	Namkulanga		0	10	10	0	0	4	1	1	1	1	5	3	4	1	0	Kole Kole	Ngumi		0	1		0 G5_Long line_Mkulanga	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G5		Mahipi wakulumbu Longlines	Mehui		0	10	10	0	4	4	1	1	1	1	4	3	3	1	0	Kole Kole	Ngumi		0	1		0 G5_Long line_Mehui	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G5		Mahipi wakulumbu Longlines	Nachujwe		0	10	8	0	4	0	1	1	1	1	4	3	3	1	0	Vibua	Kelea		0	1		0 G5_Long line_Nachujwe	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G5		Mahipi wakulumbu Longlines	Mnuli		0	10	0	0	10	0	1	1	1	1	5	5	5	1	0	Changu	Songolo		0	1		0 G5_Long line_Mnuli	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G5		Mahipi wakulumbu Longlines	Ng'ongolo		10	10	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	4	3	3	1	0	Chewa	Taii		0	1		0 G5_Long line_Ng'ongolo	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G5		Mahipi wakulumbu Longlines	Kinini		10	4	0	8	0	0	1	1	1	1	5	5	5	1	0	Changu	Taii		0	1		1 G5_Longline_Kinini	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G5		Mahipi wakulumbu Longlines	Jimbeini		10	0	0	10	0	0	1	1	1	1	4	5	5	1	0	Changu	Taii		0	1		0 G5_Longline_Jimbeini	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ	
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Nachujwe		0	10	0	0	8	10	0	0	0	0	3	3	4	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Nachujwe	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Kwa Jaba		0	10	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	3	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Kwajaba	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Kitomungu		0	10	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	4	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Kitomungu	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Mnuli		0	10	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	3	0	1					0	1		0 G14_Gleaning_Kwammuli	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Ng'ongolo		0	10	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	3	0	1					0	1		0 G14_Gleaning_Ng'ongolo	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Melini		10	0	0	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	4	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Melini	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Magoyoyoyo		10	10	0	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	3	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Mikoko mitatu	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Mikoko mitatu		10	10	0	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	4	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Magoyoyoyo	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Kwa Said Alidi		0	10	10	0	8	8	0	0	0	0	4	4	5	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Kwa saidi Halidi	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Jwe la Ngulawa		0	10	10	0	8	8	0	0	0	0	5	5	5	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Jwe la ngulawa	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Mawe Mavule		0	0	10	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	4	3	4	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Mawe mavule	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Kinini		0	0	10	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	3	3	3	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Kinini	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ
01/21/2024	Kijwani, Mvuleni mashariki, & Maloo G14		Waterbea kwa mgi Gleaning	Namkadabwe		0	0	10	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	3	2	3	0	1					0	0		1 G14_Gleaning_Namkadabwe	KIHMVUMALO_KMZ

Appendix 5: Example of primary maps

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Appendix 6: Example of relative usage map and data set

Appendix 7: List of participants during Focus Group Discussions

[Available here](#)